

Use of phytoalexin-inducing chemicals to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

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We tested three chemicals that have been found to be highly effective against brown spot and blast infections for their effect on ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Grains of susceptible cultivar Cauvery were soaked in aqueous solutions of sodium selenite (10^{-5} M), ferric chloride (10^{-4} M), and cycloheximide (10^{-6} M) for 24 h before sowing in 20-cm pots, with three replications per treatment. Water-soaked grains were used as the control. Six-week-old plants (5/pot) were artificially inoculated by inserting sclerotium into the leaf sheath. ShB

Effect of seed treatment with phytoalexin-inducing chemicals on ShB disease in rice.^a Kalyani, India, 1988.

Treatment	Disease score ^b (0-9)		Panicles (no./plant)	Filled grains (no./plant)	100-grain wt (g)
	2 wk	3 wk			
Control (healthy)	—	—	3.67	120	2.2
Control (inoculated)	5.6	6.6	3.27	70	1.9
Sodium selenite	3.9	5.3	3.39	78	2.0
Ferric chloride	3.8	4.7	3.47	89	2.1
Cycloheximide	3.0	3.9	3.52	96	2.1
SE(m) ±	0.2	0.4		4	
LSD (0.05)	0.5	1.2		16	
LSD (0.01)	0.7	1.8		24	

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

symptoms were assessed 2 and 3 wk after inoculation.

All three chemicals significantly reduced ShB symptoms (see table). Panicle numbers, filled grains/plant, and 100-grain weight improved with treatment, in line with symptom inhibition. When the experiment was

repeated, results were the same.

These results support the view that phytoalexin-inducing chemicals confer general resistance on rice plants, possibly through activation of innate defense mechanisms. The level of protection may not be the same against different pathogens. □

Sensitivity of three sclerotial rice pathogens to plant oils

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Three sclerotial fungi were isolated and purified on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium. Sclerotia were harvested from 1-mo-old cultures. Plant oils from neem *Azadirachta indica*, mahua *Madhuca indica*, karanja *Pongamia glabra*, and citronella *Cymbopogon nardus* were emulsified with Tween-80.

Sclerotia were soaked in 5% plant oil emulsion (POE) and allowed to germinate on sterilized wheat grains in petri plates. Each plate contained 10 sclerotia. The plates were incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 48 h.

Neem and citronella oils strongly inhibited germination of sclerotia of all

Effect of plant oils on germination of sclerotia (av of 4 replications). West Bengal, India.

Fungus	Germination (%)				
	Control	Neem	Mahua	Karanja	Citronella
<i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>	0	80	40	50	80
<i>Rhizoctonia oryzae-sativae</i>	0	100	0	70	100
<i>Sclerotium hydrophyllum</i>	20	100	20	20	100
LSD (0.01)					
Oil	3.108				
Fungus	13.803				
Oil × fungus	26.73				

fungi; mahua oil had no inhibitory activity (see table). Karanja oil was effective only against *Rhizoctonia oryzae-sativae* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

In another experiment, PDA medium was amended with 5% oil emulsified with 0.1% emulsifier in total volume. The center of each plate was inoculated with a 5-d-old culture of the fungi. Growth of fungi diameter was measured. Citronella, neem, and karanja showed similar types of inhibition against fungi growth; mahua had little result (see figure). □

Effect of plant oils on growth of sclerotial fungi, West Bengal, India. SR = *S. rolfsii*, RO = *R. oryzae-sativae*, SH = *S. hydrophyllum*.